

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEXICAL UNITS IN COMMUNICATION

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LUG’AVIY BIRLIKLARNING MULOQOTDAGI AHAMIYATI

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ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ В ОБЩЕНИИ

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada dunyo tilshunosligida hozirgi kunda til taraqqiyotining asosiy manbai hisoblangan neologizmlarni semantikderivation, integrativ, lingvokulturologik, semantikkommunikativ, lingvokognitiv, funksional-pragmatik, psixolingvistik va sociolingvistik aspektlarda tadqiq etish yo’nalishlarida izlanishlar olib borilayotgani hamda lug’aviy birliklarning muloqotdagi ahamiyati haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: Leksik birliklar, til, o’rgatish, ijtimoiy, o’rganish, usullar, muhit, jarayon, salbiy ta’sir, tovushlar, transpozisiya, bilim, ko’nikma, malaka, aloqa

Аннотация: В данной статье исследования проводятся в направлениях исследования неологизмов, которые в настоящее время считаются основным источником развития языка в мировой лингвистике, в семантическом словообразовательном, интегративном, лингвокультурном, семантико-коммуникативном, лингвокогнитивном, функционально-прагматическом,

ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОМ И СОЦИОЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ, а также значение лексических единиц в общении.

Ключевые слова: Лексические единицы, язык, обучение, социальное, обучение, методы, окружающая среда, процесс, негативное влияние, звуки, транспозиция, знания, навыки, компетентность, общение.

Abstract: In this article, research is being carried out in the directions of researching neologisms, which are currently considered the main source of language development in world linguistics, in semantic derivational, integrative, linguocultural, semantic-communicative, linguocognitive, functional-pragmatic, psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic aspects, as well as the importance of lexical units in communication.

Key words: Lexical units, language, teach, social, learn, methods, environment, process, negative influence, sounds, transposition, knowledge, skills, competence, communication.

In recent years, our country has gone on the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and social life, because in the current era, when time is rapidly developing, the state that relies on new ideas, new ideas, and innovation wins. In world linguistics, the problem of continuous innovation processes in the language system has never lost its relevance. Especially in the last decades of the 20th century and the first decades of the 21st century, there were drastic changes, radical changes, and unprecedented updates in various aspects of social life. Extra linguistic factors such as the reunification of Germany, the establishment of the European Union, the rapid development of information and communication technologies, the processes of globalization and integration have led to the acceleration of innovation processes in the German language vocabulary, the enrichment of the language through neologisms, as a result of which their special study is more has become an urgent issue.

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Currently, in world linguistics, research is being conducted in the directions of researching neologisms, which are considered the main source of language development, in semantic derivational, integrative, linguacultural, semantic-communicative, linguacognitive, functional-pragmatic, psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic aspects. Despite the fact that researches are being conducted on issues such as the role of everyday colloquial speech in the current German language system, the specific features of the development of its vocabulary, the creation of new vocabulary units through non-standard methods, and their variants, neologisms are. There are ambiguous situations and aspects that need to be studied in the context of conversational speech. In the recent period, the main attention is paid to the study of speech phenomena that express the conflicts in the language system in the science of linguistics. There are always conflicts in the language system that cannot be foreseen by any criteria.

The specific features of the development of its vocabulary, the creation of new lexical units through non-standard methods, and their variability, there are unclear situations and aspects that need to be study regarding the research of lexical units within the framework of colloquial speech.¹⁶ Expressiveness, emotionality, imagery, evaluation, etc., are important problems, because their solution provides an opportunity for a deeper study of the fundamental issues of the new lexical meaning. Also, while explaining the essence of new lexical units, the specificity of their semantics and the mechanisms of their creation, the process of the emergence of lexical units, the research methods of lexical and phraseological materials of different styles, it creates a basis for the comprehensive study of the new lexicon in texts and dictionaries.

The relevance of this issue is determined by studying the pragmatic factors of speech activity.¹⁷

¹⁶Ахмедов Анвар. Тил луғат таркибининг янгиланиш жараёнлари лингвистик муаммо сифатида. Монография. Қарши. «Intellekt» нашриёти, 2022. – 4-5 б.

¹⁷ Болотнова Н.С. Основы теории текста: Пособие для учителей и студентовфилологов педагогического университета. – Томск: Изд-во Том. гос. пед. ун-та, 1999. – С.15-18; Бушуй А.М. Язык и действительность. – Ташкент: Фан, 2005. – С.41

The members of the language-using society take advantage of these contradictions and create an innovation that represents a departure from the norm during a certain period of language development. However, innovation is not a mistake in the language, because the norm does not fully cover the activities of the language, all its practical applications.

Human experience is concentrated in information. People's memory, history and traditions are embodied in it. At the same time, it also carries a certain innovation in terms of strengthening the exchange of communication between individuals and regulating the processes of the emergence of words.

Each type of communication requires a specific situation. In fact, written mass communication is characterized by a communication situation in which the participants of the dialogue perform through a specific speech object. As a result, this type of communication takes the form of indirect communication, which is further complicated by the distance of the participants in terms of space and time and the presence of an intermediary person. The mediator plays an important role in the communicative act of written mass communication. For example, in written advertisements that are constantly used in everyday life, a copywriting bureau is an intermediary. The intermediary receives the relevant content information from the advertiser.¹⁸

It is distinguished by taking into account the communication process from all sides, paying attention to speech creativity, the language and style of the "speech work", and the interaction between individuals in the exchange of information through the medium of language. At the same time, also a consistency envisages scientific research related to the generalization of the new lexicon and the study of new meaning features in the communicative act, which is one of the important areas in the aspects of general language practice.

In conclusion, communication is a social activity and belongs to the system of types of purposeful human activity. Therefore, it is a social phenomenon in terms of

¹⁸ Ахмедов Анвар. Тил луғат таркибининг янгиланиш жараёнлари лингвистик муаммо сифатида. Монография. Қарши. «Intellect» нашриёти, 2022. – 33-36 б.

its occurrence, nature, development laws. The purpose of communication is social communication, which tends to influence society. In this way, the characteristic of human communication is determined. Relative completeness of thought in terms of content and grammar, in general, is the basis of any conscious communication. The main condition for the use of any language unit is its completeness in terms of form and content. This completeness is ensured by the legal connections of independent and auxiliary words. The first unit of language studied in the communicative aspect is the thought, which is the reason for its recognition as the initial category of any linguistic analysis. The interrelationship of language units is precisely the context that occurs simultaneously with the process of formation of each word, construction and thought. The use of any language unit requires the description of its immediate environment. In particular, it is required to analyze the complete thought as the smallest communicative link and device at the layer of the phrase.

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